

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17601190

Public Sector Budgetary Control And Fiscal Sustainability In Nigeria

Ven. Prof. Joshua K. J. Onuora¹, Ezugwu, David Chukwuka², Okonta, Chukwuekwu Nordi³ & Oseji, Stephen Chigoziem⁴

¹⁻⁴Department of Accountancy,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria
E-mail: ²⁻³chukwukad8@gmail.com, nordichuks@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of public sector budgetary control on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. Specifically, the study investigates how annual operating budget control, revenue budget variance analysis, and budget monitoring influence fiscal sustainability. A survey research design was adopted, targeting a population of 720,000 public sector employees, from which a sample of 400 respondents was selected using the snowball sampling technique. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency and mean, while multiple regression analysis was employed to test the research hypotheses. The findings revealed that: annual operating budget control has a positive and significant effect on fiscal sustainability ($\beta = 0.236$, $p = 0.000$); revenue budget variance analysis has a positive and significant effect on fiscal sustainability ($\beta = 0.129$, $p = 0.016$); budget monitoring has a positive and significant effect on fiscal sustainability ($\beta = 0.290$, $p = 0.000$). The study concludes that effective budgetary control mechanisms enhance fiscal discipline and sustainability in the Nigerian public sector, and therefore recommends that management teams in Nigerian public sector organizations should strengthen the preparation and implementation of annual operating budgets by ensuring that budget plans are comprehensive, realistic, and aligned with organizational objectives. This would help guide financial decisions more effectively, ensure optimal allocation of resources, and support long-term fiscal sustainability.

Keywords: Public Sector Budgetary Control, Fiscal Sustainability, Annual Operating Budget Control, Revenue Budget Variance Analysis, Budget Monitoring

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Public financial management has become one of the most crucial aspects of governance in modern economies. Governments all over the world rely on sound budgeting systems to ensure the efficient allocation and utilization of public resources. In developing countries like Nigeria, the challenge of managing scarce financial resources amid growing social and economic demands has heightened the need for effective budgetary control (Mobosi & Okonta, 2025; Nwoko, Okuma & Ugwu, 2022). The budget serves as a financial roadmap that guides the execution of government policies and projects, but its success depends largely on how well it is controlled and monitored. In recent years, Nigeria has experienced recurrent budget deficits, rising public debt (Nwoye et al., 2023), and poor fiscal outcomes despite large budgetary allocations (Ajibola et al., 2024). These challenges have raised serious concerns about the sustainability of public finances and the transparency of government spending (Anyanwu & Ananwude, 2021). The implementation of budgetary control mechanisms within the public sector,

therefore, has become a focal point in addressing issues related to financial accountability, fiscal discipline, and sustainable development (Ugwu, Eboatu & Nwoko, 2022). The growing demand for efficiency in public spending and the need to restore public confidence in government financial management make it essential to investigate how budgetary control practices affect fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.

Akayuri et al. (2025) argued that public sector budgetary control is a vital management tool that ensures government expenditures are consistent with approved financial plans and available revenue. It helps public managers to identify deviations between planned and actual performance, thereby enabling timely corrective actions. According to Adrison (2024), fiscal sustainability, on the other hand, refers to a government's ability to sustain its spending patterns and service its obligations without resorting to excessive borrowing or compromising future fiscal stability. In today's economic environment, characterized by revenue volatility, inflationary pressures, and high public debt levels, fiscal sustainability has become a major policy concern (Ezekwe, 2025; Ugwu, Eboatu & Nwoko, 2022). Nigeria is like many other developing nations, faces persistent fiscal imbalances due to fluctuations in oil revenues, rising personnel costs, and weak institutional capacity for financial control. Budgetary control mechanisms, such as annual operating budget control, revenue budget variance analysis, and budget monitoring, are designed to ensure that government spending aligns with fiscal objectives and revenue projections (Ogbu & Ugwu 2016b; Ugwu, et al., 2022). Their effective application promotes transparency, accountability, and value for money in public administration (Dusabimana & Kiptanui, 2025; Nwoko, et al., 2022). As governments strive to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals and meet citizens' expectations, maintaining fiscal sustainability through prudent budgeting and effective control has become a priority in public financial management discourse (Ogbu & Ugwu 2016b).

The relationship between public sector budgetary control and fiscal sustainability is an area of growing interest among scholars and policymakers. When government institutions establish effective budgetary control systems, they are better positioned to monitor the flow of public funds, prevent waste, and ensure that budget implementation aligns with fiscal targets (Augustine, 2022; Ugwu, Eboatu & Nwoko, 2022). This, in turn, enhances fiscal sustainability by reducing the likelihood of unplanned deficits and excessive borrowing. In contrast, weak budgetary control often results in financial mismanagement, corruption, and budget overruns that undermine fiscal stability (Ajibola et al., 2024; Nwangwu, Ozigbo, Ngige & Ugwu, 2020). In Nigeria, several fiscal responsibility measures, such as the Fiscal Responsibility Act of 2007 and the Treasury Single Account (TSA), were introduced to improve budgetary discipline and strengthen the link between budget execution and fiscal sustainability (Ogbu & Ugwu 2016b). However, despite these reforms, cases of poor budget performance and fiscal indiscipline persist in many institutions (Danladi & Danladi, 2023). The recurring issues of inflated contracts, abandoned projects, and delayed budget implementation have continued to weaken the nation's fiscal position. Therefore, a systematic assessment of how public sector budgetary control influences fiscal sustainability is essential to understanding the extent to which these control mechanisms are effective in achieving their intended outcomes (Nwoko, et al., 2022).

In a properly managed public financial system, government budgets are prepared, implemented, and controlled to ensure that resources are allocated efficiently and expenditures are kept within approved limits. Akayuri et al. (2025) argued that budgetary control helps public sector institutions to plan their operations, monitor performance, and evaluate results against established financial objectives. Through regular variance analysis and monitoring, public managers are able to detect deviations early and take corrective action to maintain fiscal stability. When effectively practiced, budgetary control ensures accountability, transparency, and prudent management of public funds (Ugwu & Nwakoby, 2021; Nwoko, et al., 2022). This supports fiscal sustainability by preventing unnecessary borrowing and enabling the government to meet its financial obligations without compromising long-term development goals (Mobosi & Okonta, 2025). In such a situation, the budget serves as a reliable tool for guiding economic policy, managing public debt, and promoting the efficient delivery of public services.

However, in Nigeria, public sector budgeting and financial management have not been conducted in strict adherence to control procedures. Cases of poor budget implementation, weak monitoring mechanisms,

and inaccurate revenue projections are common across many ministries, departments, and agencies (Ajibola et al., 2024). Deviations between approved budgets and actual performance often go uncorrected, resulting in recurrent deficits and mounting public debt. Although the government has introduced reforms such as the Fiscal Responsibility Act, the Treasury Single Account, and the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS), financial indiscipline continues to weaken fiscal management. Budgetary control practices such as variance analysis, expenditure tracking, and performance review are often poorly executed or ignored (Ugwu, et al., 2022; Ogbu & Ugwu 2016b). Consequently, funds are frequently misallocated, while many projects remain uncompleted or abandoned due to inadequate control over financial operations.

The continued disregard for budgetary control principles has serious implications for Nigeria's fiscal sustainability. Persistent budget deficits, rising debt servicing costs, and declining public trust in government financial management have placed significant pressure on the nation's economy. The lack of effective budget monitoring and revenue variance analysis contributes to leakages, corruption, and inefficiency in the use of public resources (Ugwu & Nwakoby, 2021; Ogbu & Ugwu 2016b). Over time, these problems reduce the government's ability to fund essential social and infrastructure projects, undermining economic growth and development (Anyanwu & Ananwude, 2021). If the situation remains unchecked, Nigeria risks facing deeper fiscal instability that could limit future investment opportunities, increase dependency on borrowing, and weaken the overall capacity of the public sector to deliver sustainable development outcomes. It is against this background that the study examines the effect of public sector budgetary control on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.

Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of public sector budgetary control on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The specific objectives are as follows:

1. To determine the effect of annual operating budget control on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.
2. To assess the effect of revenue budget variance analysis on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.
3. To evaluate the effect of budget monitoring on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Annual operating budget control has no significant effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Revenue budget variance analysis has no significant effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Budget monitoring has no significant effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Public Sector Budgetary Control

Public sector budgetary control refers to the process by which government institutions plan, regulate, and supervise the use of public funds to ensure that financial activities are consistent with approved budgets (Akayuri et al., 2025; Nwoko, et al., 2022). It serves as a systematic approach that helps public administrators compare actual financial performance with planned financial targets and make necessary adjustments when discrepancies occur. This practice ensures that every expenditure or commitment made by a public institution aligns with the financial policies, priorities, and revenue forecasts established by the government (Okorie & Campus, 2016; Ugwu, et al., 2022). In a broader sense, public sector budgetary control represents a mechanism for maintaining discipline in public financial management. It provides a structured framework for assessing whether government resources are used efficiently and for the intended purposes. Through effective control, government agencies can detect misuse of funds, prevent waste, and promote accountability in the management of public finances. Budgetary control in the public sector involves continuous evaluation of financial operations, allowing policymakers and managers to identify deviations and respond promptly (Dusabimana & Kiptanui, 2025; Ugwu & Nwakoby, 2021).

Public sector budgetary control also reflects the commitment of a government to fiscal prudence and transparency. It is a safeguard against mismanagement and corruption, ensuring that funds allocated for public projects contribute to national development goals. When properly applied, it enhances public trust and improves institutional credibility (Ajibola et al., 2024). By emphasizing adherence to spending limits

and rational decision-making, public sector budgetary control strengthens financial discipline and supports sustainable fiscal outcomes. In Nigeria, its importance has become increasingly evident as the government seeks to manage limited resources efficiently and achieve long-term fiscal stability.

Annual Operating Budget Control

Annual operating budget control refers to the process of managing and supervising the implementation of a government's approved financial plan within a fiscal year (Mobosi & Okonta, 2025). It involves comparing actual revenue and expenditure figures with budget estimates and ensuring that spending activities conform to approved limits. Through this process, public sector managers can monitor financial performance, identify deviations, and take corrective action to maintain alignment with established financial objectives (Ruliana et al., 2015; Ugwu, 2020j). This control system ensures that operational activities are executed within available resources and that financial discipline is maintained throughout the budget cycle. Annual operating budget control provides a practical means of translating policy objectives into measurable financial outcomes. It allows government institutions to assess whether funds are being used effectively to achieve planned programs and projects (Ogbu & Ugwu 2016b; Ugwu, et al., 2022). By constantly reviewing the implementation of the annual budget, managers can detect inefficiencies, delays, or irregularities in the execution of financial plans. This continuous evaluation process strengthens the accountability of public officers and improves transparency in the management of public resources.

In a well-functioning public administration, annual operating budget control acts as both a preventive and corrective tool. It helps prevent overspending and ensures that funds are utilized according to government priorities (Mobosi & Okonta, 2025; Nwoko, et al., 2022). It also provides feedback that can guide future budget preparation, making the budgeting process more realistic and evidence-based. The practice is particularly important in developing economies like Nigeria, where resource constraints and competing demands require careful financial planning. When properly enforced, annual operating budget control contributes to sound financial governance, efficient service delivery, and overall fiscal sustainability (Ugwu, 2020j).

Revenue Budget Variance Analysis

Revenue budget variance analysis involves the comparison between actual revenues collected and the revenues that were projected or budgeted for a specific period (Ajibola et al., 2024). It is a technique used to identify differences between expected and realized income, determine the causes of these differences, and evaluate their implications for financial planning. This process helps public sector organizations assess how well they are meeting their revenue targets and whether adjustments are needed in their revenue generation strategies (Sorochuk et al., 2023; Ugwu & Nwakoby, 2021). It also supports managerial decision-making by highlighting the strengths and weaknesses of existing fiscal policies. In government finance, revenue budget variance analysis is an essential instrument for maintaining financial control. It allows policymakers to track performance against revenue projections and take corrective measures when shortfalls occur. For instance, if actual revenue falls below budgeted levels, it may indicate inefficiencies in revenue collection, weak enforcement mechanisms, or an economic downturn (Nwoko, et al., 2022). Conversely, when actual revenue exceeds budget expectations, it may suggest underestimation of income sources or improved collection efficiency. Understanding these differences is crucial for ensuring that expenditure plans remain realistic and that fiscal stability is maintained (Ajibola et al., 2024; Ugwu, 2020j).

Revenue budget variance analysis also enhances accountability and transparency within public sector institutions. By providing a factual assessment of revenue performance, it enables government managers to make informed decisions about resource allocation and financial policy. Regular variance analysis ensures that revenue trends are monitored closely and that the government remains responsive to fiscal challenges (Ugwu, et al., 2022). In Nigeria, where revenue volatility, especially from oil income, has historically affected budget performance, this practice is vital for achieving fiscal balance and promoting sustainable financial management.

Budget Monitoring

Budget monitoring refers to the continuous process of tracking and supervising budget implementation to ensure that financial activities are consistent with approved plans (Dusabimana & Kiptanui, 2025). It involves observing the flow of funds, assessing expenditure patterns, and comparing actual performance with the budgeted targets. The purpose of monitoring is to ensure that resources are used efficiently and that financial decisions are guided by transparency and accountability (Danladi & Danladi, 2023). By regularly reviewing financial progress, budget monitoring helps prevent overspending, misallocation of funds, and delays in project execution. Effective budget monitoring requires accurate record-keeping, timely reporting, and the active participation of managers and auditors (Ugwu & Nwakoby, 2021). Through periodic reviews and financial reporting, government agencies can identify potential problems early and take corrective measures to improve performance. Monitoring also serves as an early warning system, allowing public sector institutions to respond promptly to emerging financial risks. It ensures that budget implementation remains aligned with policy objectives and that deviations are addressed before they become major fiscal challenges (Akeke et al., 2024).

Budget monitoring plays a crucial role in strengthening fiscal discipline within the public sector. It promotes transparency by making financial operations visible and measurable, thereby increasing public confidence in government spending (Dusabimana & Kiptanui, 2025). In addition, it supports decision-making by providing reliable data on how funds are being utilized. In countries like Nigeria, where financial mismanagement and weak institutional oversight have hindered effective governance, regular and systematic budget monitoring is essential. It not only improves accountability but also enhances the efficiency and credibility of public financial management systems (Ugwu, 2020j).

Fiscal Sustainability

Fiscal sustainability refers to a government's capacity to maintain its current spending, tax policies, and other financial commitments without jeopardizing its long-term fiscal stability (Adrison, 2024). It implies that the government can continue to meet its obligations—such as debt servicing, public investment, and recurrent expenditure—without resorting to excessive borrowing or creating economic instability. A fiscally sustainable government balances revenue generation and expenditure in a manner that supports steady economic growth while minimizing financial vulnerability (Mobosi & Okonta, 2025; Ugwu, 2020j). The concept emphasizes the importance of responsible fiscal management and long-term planning. It requires maintaining a sustainable debt level, ensuring adequate revenue mobilization, and controlling public spending. When fiscal sustainability is achieved, the government is able to deliver essential services, invest in infrastructure, and respond effectively to economic shocks (Ugwu & Nwakoby, 2021). Conversely, when fiscal sustainability is threatened, the government faces growing deficits, rising debt burdens, and reduced capacity to finance public programs. For developing countries like Nigeria, ensuring fiscal sustainability has become a pressing challenge due to unstable revenue sources, especially dependence on oil, and weak budgetary discipline.

Fiscal sustainability also encompasses intergenerational equity, which ensures that current fiscal policies do not impose an unfair financial burden on future generations (Ezekwe, 2025). It calls for efficient allocation of resources and prudent financial management that promotes stability and growth over time (Anyanwu & Ananwude, 2021; Ugwu & Nwakoby, 2021). Sustained fiscal health enhances investor confidence, strengthens macroeconomic stability, and improves the government's ability to deliver long-term development goals. Therefore, maintaining fiscal sustainability is central to achieving economic resilience and ensuring that public sector financial practices contribute to lasting national development.

Theoretical Framework

The stewardship theory was developed in the field of management during the 1980s and was formally articulated by Donaldson and Davis in 1991 (Badara, 2017). The theory emerged as a response to the limitations of agency theory, which assumes that managers are primarily motivated by self-interest. Stewardship theory, instead, presents a more optimistic view of managerial behavior by suggesting that managers are trustworthy individuals who can be relied upon to act in the best interest of the organization they serve. The theory was influenced by human relations and organizational behavior perspectives,

which emphasize the importance of intrinsic motivation, commitment, and shared goals within institutions. Over time, the theory has been applied beyond the private sector and has gained relevance in public administration and governance, where the management of public resources requires accountability, responsibility, and ethical conduct (Onyebu, Ugwu, Oluwafemi & Agbo, 2020)..

The main postulation of stewardship theory is that individuals, particularly managers, are motivated by the need to perform their duties with integrity, achieve organizational objectives, and ensure collective success rather than pursue personal gains (Torfinng & Bentzen, 2020). It assumes that managers view themselves as stewards of resources entrusted to them, acting in alignment with the goals and values of the institution. This perspective emphasizes trust, empowerment, and accountability as guiding principles of management (Okwaro, 2014). The theory also argues that when managers are trusted and given the necessary authority to perform their roles effectively, they are more likely to act responsibly and deliver better outcomes. In essence, stewardship theory highlights the relationship between good governance, effective leadership, and organizational performance by suggesting that individuals derive satisfaction and recognition from fulfilling their responsibilities rather than from personal enrichment (Onyebu, et al., 2020)..

The relevance of stewardship theory to this study lies in its focus on accountability, integrity, and responsible management of public resources. In the context of public sector budgeting, stewardship theory provides a moral and behavioral foundation for understanding how government officials and financial managers should handle public funds. It supports the view that when public officers perceive themselves as stewards of the nation's financial resources, they are more likely to implement effective budgetary control systems that promote transparency and fiscal discipline. By aligning individual responsibility with institutional goals, the theory helps explain how strong budgetary control practices can enhance fiscal sustainability (Nwangwu, et al., 2020). Therefore, stewardship theory provides the philosophical basis for this study by emphasizing that sustainable fiscal management in Nigeria depends not only on financial regulations but also on the ethical commitment of public officials to act as faithful stewards of the public trust.

Empirical Review

Dusabimana and Kiptanui (2025) investigated how budgetary control practices influence the financial sustainability of the AIDS Healthcare Foundation (AHF) in Rwanda. Their study was guided by the Resource-Based View and Control Theories, emphasizing the importance of budget monitoring and evaluation in ensuring efficient resource utilization and organizational performance. Using a descriptive research design that combined quantitative and qualitative methods, data were collected from 132 participants through questionnaires and interviews. Analysis conducted with SPSS revealed a strong positive relationship between budget monitoring and project performance, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.705$. The regression analysis further confirmed that budget monitoring significantly predicts project performance, indicating that systematic financial supervision contributes to sustainable outcomes. The researchers concluded that applying both theoretical perspectives enhances accountability, promotes the strategic use of internal resources, and strengthens long-term financial stability within nonprofit organizations.

Mobosi and Okonta (2025) analyzed how revenue structures and budgetary choices affect the fiscal sustainability index of Nigeria's 36 state governments between 2012 and 2020. Employing a two-step Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimation, they discovered that Lagos and Rivers States ranked highest in fiscal viability, while Osun ranked lowest. The study found that fiscal stability tends to persist over time, meaning states that maintain sound fiscal policies are likely to continue doing so. Results also showed that budgetary choices had a positive, though statistically insignificant, impact on fiscal sustainability, while revenue structure exerted a negative and significant effect. Their findings suggest that revenue management and fiscal decision-making must be aligned to ensure sustainable fiscal performance. Furthermore, a bidirectional relationship was found between state governments' annual operating budgets and fiscal sustainability, highlighting the mutual dependence between budgeting practices and long-term fiscal health.

Taiwo et al. (2025) assessed the determinants of fiscal policy sustainability in Nigeria using data from 1971 to 2023 sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. Applying the ARDL Cointegration approach, the study discovered that in the short term, fluctuations in government expenditure significantly affected both primary balance and debt-to-GDP ratios. Temporary changes in GDP and lagged debt ratios also showed significant relationships with fiscal indicators, indicating the sensitivity of fiscal balance to expenditure and income dynamics. In the long term, however, the influence of temporary government spending was negative and statistically insignificant, reflecting weak compliance with fiscal responsibility principles over time. The study concluded that fiscal sustainability in Nigeria requires more disciplined expenditure management, improved revenue generation, and reduced dependence on external borrowing to avoid the accumulation of unsustainable debt.

Akpanowo and Mbobo (2025) examined the influence of the Fiscal Responsibility Act on budgeting and fiscal discipline within Nigeria's public sector. The research used a survey design and gathered primary data from a purposively selected sample of 55 respondents out of 500 employees from the Ministry of Finance. The study employed ordinary least squares regression for hypothesis testing using SPSS software. Findings indicated that the Fiscal Responsibility Act significantly influences budget implementation, fiscal discipline, and corruption control. The results suggest that strengthening the enforcement of fiscal responsibility laws enhances transparency and accountability in government operations. The authors recommended continuous monitoring and evaluation to ensure compliance with the Act and periodic reviews to update its provisions to meet emerging fiscal challenges.

Agor et al. (2024) studied how Nigeria's federal budget deficits influence long-term economic growth and stability between 2003 and 2023. Using a Generalized Least Squares model, the study explored relationships between economic growth and variables such as domestic debt, external grants, external debt servicing, and emergency government expenditures. Grounded in Keynesian economics, the study observed that domestic debt positively affects growth when used to fund productive investments. However, while external grants had a positive yet statistically insignificant effect, external debt servicing and emergency spending were found to negatively influence economic performance. The results suggest that excessive reliance on debt servicing and unplanned expenditures undermines growth, while strategic use of debt can promote development if effectively managed.

Ajibola et al. (2024) analyzed the relationship between budgetary control and financial management within Nigeria's public sector using secondary data from various governmental sources. Descriptive and panel regression analyses revealed that revenue budget variance analysis and tax compliance rates both have positive and significant effects on public finances. The results further indicated that conducting variance analysis of revenue budgets strengthens government financial health and enhances fiscal stability. The study concluded that effective budgetary control practices, such as variance analysis and improved tax compliance, are critical to sound public financial management in Nigeria.

Nestor and David (2023) explored the effect of government budget implementation on economic growth in Nigeria using data covering the period 1981 to 2021. Economic growth, represented by GDP, was examined against capital and recurrent expenditures, exchange rate, and gross fixed capital formation using the ARDL model. Findings revealed that poor budget implementation causes short-run instability, although economic growth tends to converge toward equilibrium by approximately 37.55 percent over time. In the short run, capital expenditure and investment in fixed capital positively influenced growth, while recurrent expenditure and exchange rate volatility had negative effects. In the long run, recurrent expenditure became a positive and significant driver of growth, suggesting that improved budget execution enhances overall economic performance.

Danladi and Danladi (2023) investigated how budgetary control influences the financial performance of nonprofit organizations in Nigeria. Adopting a cross-sectional survey design, data were gathered from 143 registered NGOs through structured questionnaires. Using multiple linear regression for analysis, the study found that budget formulation, monitoring, and flexibility significantly affect financial performance, while budget implementation had no significant effect. The researchers concluded that effective budgetary control frameworks are essential for improving the financial outcomes of NGOs.

They recommended that organizations adopt modern financial management technologies to strengthen monitoring and accountability processes.

Augustine (2022) explored budgeting techniques and control in local governments with a focus on participatory budgeting as a tool for sustainable development. Using an exploratory approach, the study emphasized fairness, transparency, and accountability in resource allocation. Findings showed that participatory budgeting promotes community involvement, enhances transparency, and improves service delivery. The study recommended that local governments strengthen internal control mechanisms, ensure stakeholder involvement in budget formulation, and adopt effective monitoring systems to promote performance-based governance.

Wanga (2022) examined the link between budgetary control and financial sustainability among local NGOs in Kenya, focusing on budgeting techniques and their outcomes. The research, guided by budgeting and responsibility accounting theories, collected both primary and secondary data from 60 finance officers and analysts across 30 organizations. Descriptive and regression analyses revealed that budgetary control positively influences financial sustainability, explaining 56% of variations in sustainability indicators. Among the studied variables, planning had the strongest effect, demonstrating that well-structured budgeting processes improve resource utilization and long-term financial stability.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey research design. The survey design is deemed appropriate as it enables the researcher to collect primary data from a cross-section of respondents in various public sector institutions across Nigeria (Ikwo et al., 2024; Nworie & Onwuka, 2023; Ugwu & Nwakoby, 2021). This design is suitable for investigating the relationship between public sector budgetary control mechanisms and fiscal sustainability. It allows for efficient data collection and provides a basis for generalizing the findings to the broader population of public sector institutions.

The study's target population comprises 720,000 employees working within Nigeria's public sector institutions at federal level (The Punch, 2023). This population represents personnel involved in budgeting, finance, accounting, and administrative operations that influence budgetary control and fiscal sustainability. Given the vast nature of the public sector and the challenges in accessing a complete sampling frame, the study employed a snowball sampling technique. This approach allows the researcher to identify initial respondents knowledgeable about public budgeting processes, who then refer others with similar expertise or roles. Snowballing was particularly suitable due to the dispersion of public sector employees across various government institutions.

The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane (1973) formula with a 5% margin of error:

$$\text{Formula: Sample size (n)} = \frac{N}{1+N(\epsilon)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

NN = population size (720,000)

e = margin of error (0.05)

$$n = \frac{720,000}{1+720,000(0.05)^2}$$

n = 400

Primary data were obtained through the administration of a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of close-ended questions designed on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from *Very High Extent (5)* to *Very Low Extent (1)*. The items were structured to measure respondents' perceptions of the effect of public sector budgetary control (using proxies such as annual operating budget control, revenue budget variance analysis, and budget monitoring) on fiscal sustainability. To ensure the validity of the instrument, both face and construct validity were established. Experts in public finance, accounting, and research methodology reviewed the questionnaire for clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness. Construct validity was achieved by aligning questionnaire items with the study's theoretical framework and objectives.

The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach’s Alpha. A pilot study was conducted with 30 public sector employees outside the main study area. The Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients for all variables exceeded the recommended 0.70 threshold, indicating satisfactory internal consistency and reliability.

Table 3.1 Reliability Test

Variable	Acronym	Cronbach’s Alpha
Fiscal Sustainability	FS	.871
Annual Operating Budget Control	AOBC	.742
Revenue Budget Variance Analysis	RBVA	.733
Budget Monitoring	BM	.857

Source: SPSS Output (2025)

To test the research hypotheses, the study employed a multiple linear regression model, specified as follows:

$$FS = \beta_0 + \beta_1AOBC + \beta_2RBVA + \beta_3BM + \mu \text{_____} \text{eqn1}$$

Where:

FS = Fiscal Sustainability (Dependent Variable), AOBC = Annual Operating Budget Control, RBVA = Revenue Budget Variance Analysis, BM = Budget Monitoring, β_0 = Intercept, β_1 - β_3 = Regression Coefficients, μ = Error Term.

Data collected were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and means were used to summarize respondents’ demographic characteristics and preliminary responses. To test the study hypotheses, multiple regression analysis was applied to determine the effect of public sector budgetary control proxies on fiscal sustainability. The significance of regression coefficients was tested at a 5% significance level ($p < 0.05$). The decision criterion for hypothesis testing was as follows:

- If $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, indicating that the independent variable has a statistically significant effect on fiscal sustainability.
- If $p\text{-value} \geq 0.05$, fail to reject the null hypothesis, implying no significant effect.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Descriptive Analysis

Out of the 400 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 397 were correctly completed and returned. This represents a response rate of 99.3 percent, which was considered adequate for analysis.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

A	Annual Operating Budget Control	VLE	LE	N	HE	VHE	Mean
1	Our organization prepares and implements an annual operating budget to guide financial decisions.	4	60	82	169	82	3.67
2	The annual operating budget effectively allocates resources across departments.	4	50	77	184	82	3.73
3	Deviations from the annual budget are promptly identified and addressed.	4	87	98	146	62	3.44
4	Annual budget control helps improve our organization’s overall financial performance.	0	71	106	178	42	3.48
B	Revenue Budget Variance Analysis	VLE	LE	N	HE	VHE	Mean
5	Variance analysis is conducted regularly to compare actual and budgeted revenues.	14	76	119	142	46	3.33
6	The organization investigates significant revenue variances to identify their causes.	8	70	104	155	60	3.48
7	Findings from variance analysis are used to enhance revenue forecasting accuracy.	16	50	93	176	62	3.55
8	Revenue variance analysis helps management make timely corrective actions.	4	54	94	175	70	3.64
C	Budget Monitoring	VLE	LE	N	HE	VHE	Mean
9	Budget performance is tracked regularly to ensure adherence to	4	54	90	197	52	3.60

	financial plans.						
10	Managers are held accountable for monitoring and controlling their departmental budgets.	8	116	80	157	36	3.24
11	The organization uses technology or software tools to monitor budget performance.	12	86	102	165	32	3.30
12	Regular budget monitoring enhances financial transparency and accountability.	4	48	58	212	75	3.77
D	Fiscal Sustainability	VLE	LE	N	HE	VHE	Mean
13	The organization maintains a balance between revenue generation and expenditure.	0	42	62	215	78	3.83
14	Our fiscal policies promote long-term financial stability.	0	44	80	210	63	3.74
15	Efforts are made to reduce financial risks that could affect future operations.	51	100	65	105	76	3.14
16	The organization’s budgeting practices contribute to its fiscal sustainability.	5	56	85	169	82	3.67

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics on public sector budgetary control and fiscal sustainability. The results show how respondents rated various aspects of budget control and financial management within their organizations. For the first item under Annual Operating Budget Control, most respondents, representing 169 and 82 respectively, agreed to a high and very high extent that their organizations prepare and implement annual operating budgets to guide financial decisions, resulting in a mean score of 3.67. Similarly, the second item shows a strong affirmation, as 184 and 82 respondents agreed to a high and very high extent that the annual budget effectively allocates resources across departments, with a mean of 3.73. For the third item, a moderate response was observed, with 146 respondents agreeing to a high extent and 62 to a very high extent that deviations from the annual budget are promptly identified and addressed, leading to a mean of 3.44. The fourth item recorded 178 and 42 respondents at the high and very high levels respectively, indicating that annual budget control contributes to improved financial performance, with a mean of 3.48.

In the section on Revenue Budget Variance Analysis, responses varied slightly. For the fifth item, a total of 142 and 46 respondents agreed to a high and very high extent respectively that variance analysis is conducted regularly to compare actual and budgeted revenues, resulting in a mean of 3.33. The sixth item showed stronger support, with 155 and 60 respondents indicating high and very high agreement that the organization investigates significant revenue variances, yielding a mean of 3.48. The seventh item recorded 176 and 62 respondents at the high and very high levels respectively, confirming that findings from variance analysis are used to enhance revenue forecasting accuracy, with a mean of 3.55. Similarly, the eighth item had 175 and 70 respondents at high and very high levels respectively, reflecting that variance analysis aids timely corrective actions, with a mean of 3.64.

Regarding Budget Monitoring, the results suggest that most organizations engage in regular monitoring activities. The ninth item recorded 197 respondents at a high extent and 52 at a very high extent, showing that budget performance is closely tracked to ensure adherence to financial plans, with a mean of 3.60. For the tenth item, 157 respondents agreed to a high extent and 36 to a very high extent that managers are held accountable for monitoring their departmental budgets, producing a mean of 3.24. The eleventh item showed a similar pattern, with 165 and 32 respondents at high and very high levels respectively, indicating that technology or software tools are used for budget monitoring, giving a mean of 3.30. The twelfth item recorded the strongest positive response, as 212 and 75 respondents agreed to a high and very high extent respectively that regular budget monitoring enhances transparency and accountability, resulting in a mean of 3.77.

For Fiscal Sustainability, the responses indicate a generally positive perception of fiscal practices. The thirteenth item shows that 215 and 78 respondents agreed to a high and very high extent that their organizations maintain a balance between revenue and expenditure, with a mean of 3.83, the highest among all items. The fourteenth item also had strong agreement, with 210 and 63 respondents at high and

very high levels respectively, suggesting that fiscal policies promote long-term stability, with a mean of 3.74. For the fifteenth item, responses were more divided, as 105 and 76 respondents agreed to a high and very high extent respectively that efforts are made to reduce financial risks, though a significant number, 151, indicated low or neutral levels, resulting in a mean of 3.14. The sixteenth item shows a generally favorable view, with 169 and 82 respondents agreeing to a high and very high extent respectively that budgeting practices contribute to fiscal sustainability, with a mean of 3.67.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Annual operating budget control has no significant effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Revenue budget variance analysis has no significant effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Budget monitoring has no significant effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria.

Table 4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.723 ^a	.523	.519	1.793

a. Predictors: (Constant), Budget Monitoring, Annual Operating Budget Control, Revenue Budget Variance Analysis

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1385.064	3	461.688	143.545	.000 ^b
	Residual	1264.014	393	3.216		
	Total	2649.078	396			

a. Dependent Variable: Fiscal Sustainability

b. Predictors: (Constant), Budget Monitoring, Annual Operating Budget Control, Revenue Budget Variance Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.150	.454		11.348	.000
	Annual Operating Budget Control	.236	.049	.300	4.844	.000
	Revenue Budget Variance Analysis	.129	.053	.160	2.418	.016
	Budget Monitoring	.290	.034	.371	8.455	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Fiscal Sustainability

Source: SPSS V. 26 (2025)

Table 4.2 presents the results of the regression analysis used to test the effect of public sector budgetary control on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The model summary shows an adjusted R-square value of 0.519, which implies that approximately 51.9 percent of the variations in fiscal sustainability can be explained by the combined effect of annual operating budget control, revenue budget variance analysis, and budget monitoring. This indicates that these three predictors together provide a substantial explanation of the changes in fiscal sustainability among the sampled public sector entities. The remaining 48.1 percent of the variation may be attributed to other factors not captured in this model, such as fiscal policy, external borrowing, or macroeconomic conditions. The ANOVA result (Sig. = 0.000) confirms that the overall regression model is statistically significant at the 5 percent level. This means that the combined effect of the three independent variables on fiscal sustainability is not due to random chance, and the model is suitable for making inferences.

The regression coefficient for the constant ($\beta = 5.150$, $p = 0.000$) indicates that when annual operating budget control, revenue budget variance analysis, and budget monitoring are held constant, the baseline value of fiscal sustainability is 5.150. This constant is statistically significant at the 5 percent level, showing that fiscal sustainability maintains a positive value even in the absence of variations in the

explanatory variables. In practical terms, it suggests that other underlying factors such as government fiscal policies or external economic conditions contribute positively to fiscal sustainability even before budgetary control mechanisms are considered.

The first hypothesis tested whether annual operating budget control has no significant effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The result shows a coefficient of $\beta = 0.236$ ($p = 0.000$), indicating that a one-unit increase in annual operating budget control leads to a 0.236 unit increase in fiscal sustainability. This marginal effect suggests that when organizations improve their annual budgeting systems, fiscal stability and prudent resource use are strengthened. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the effect is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that annual operating budget control has a significant positive effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. This means that effective preparation, implementation, and evaluation of annual budgets play a key role in promoting stable and sustainable public finances.

The second hypothesis tested whether revenue budget variance analysis has no significant effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The coefficient for this variable is $\beta = 0.129$ ($p = 0.016$), showing that a one-unit increase in revenue budget variance analysis results in a 0.129 unit increase in fiscal sustainability. This implies that as public sector organizations regularly review and analyze deviations between actual and budgeted revenues, they can make necessary corrections that enhance fiscal stability. Although the effect is smaller compared to other variables, it remains positive and statistically significant at the 5 percent level. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that revenue budget variance analysis significantly enhances fiscal sustainability. This result suggests that consistent variance reviews encourage better forecasting, reduce financial mismanagement, and improve the predictability of government revenues.

The third hypothesis tested whether budget monitoring has no significant effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The result shows a coefficient of $\beta = 0.290$ ($p = 0.000$), meaning that a one-unit improvement in budget monitoring leads to a 0.290 unit increase in fiscal sustainability. This represents the strongest effect among the three independent variables. The result implies that when organizations closely monitor budget execution, track performance, and ensure compliance with financial plans, fiscal sustainability is significantly improved. The p-value of 0.000 indicates that the effect is statistically significant at the 5 percent level. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that budget monitoring exerts a significant positive effect on fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. This finding highlights the importance of continuous oversight and accountability mechanisms in strengthening fiscal discipline and ensuring long-term financial health.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding that annual operating budget control has a positive and significant effect on fiscal sustainability ($\beta = 0.236$, $p = 0.000$) reflects the critical role that structured and well-implemented budgeting plays in ensuring the stability of public finances. When organizations meticulously prepare and follow annual budgets, they are able to allocate resources efficiently, prioritize essential expenditures, and limit wasteful spending, which collectively strengthen fiscal sustainability. This result is consistent with the findings of Mobosi and Okonta (2025), who observed a strong link between annual operating budgets and fiscal sustainability across Nigerian states, highlighting the mutual dependence between structured budget planning and long-term financial health. Similarly, Akpanowo and Mbobo (2025) reported that effective budget implementation under the Fiscal Responsibility Act enhances fiscal discipline and reduces mismanagement, reinforcing the significance of formalized budgeting. Nestor and David (2023) also found that consistent budget implementation supports economic stability by moderating short-run instabilities, while Augustine (2022) demonstrated that well-structured local government budgets, particularly participatory budgets, promote transparency and prudent resource use, which can be generalized to public sector institutions in Nigeria. These studies collectively support the view that disciplined annual budget control serves as a mechanism to guide financial decision-making, foster accountability, and contribute to sustained fiscal stability. The positive coefficient suggests that a one-unit improvement in annual operating budget control is associated with a 0.236 unit increase in fiscal sustainability, and the significance at 5% confirms the robustness of this effect.

The effect of revenue budget variance analysis on fiscal sustainability ($\beta = 0.129$, $p = 0.016$) indicates that systematic evaluation of discrepancies between actual and projected revenues enables organizations to make timely adjustments, enhancing financial predictability and stability. By identifying and addressing significant variances, management can correct deviations before they jeopardize the organization's fiscal health. This aligns with the findings of Ajibola et al. (2024), who demonstrated that conducting variance analysis improves government financial performance and strengthens fiscal stability. Similarly, Wanga (2022) found that monitoring budget deviations in Kenyan NGOs positively affected their financial sustainability, highlighting the importance of continuous revenue evaluation. Dusabimana and Kiptanui (2025) also emphasized the value of budget monitoring and evaluation in nonprofit organizations for sustaining financial outcomes. Additionally, Taiwo et al. (2025) highlighted that disciplined expenditure and accurate revenue tracking are essential for maintaining fiscal balance in Nigeria. The marginal effect of 0.129 suggests that a unit increase in revenue variance analysis is associated with a 0.129 unit increase in fiscal sustainability, and the p-value of 0.016 confirms that this effect is statistically significant.

The result showing that budget monitoring has a positive and significant effect on fiscal sustainability ($\beta = 0.290$, $p = 0.000$) highlights the importance of continuous oversight and supervision in public financial management. Regular monitoring allows management to detect deviations from budgetary plans, hold responsible parties accountable, and ensure that financial activities align with organizational goals, thereby enhancing fiscal stability. This finding resonates with Dusabimana and Kiptanui (2025), who observed that systematic monitoring and evaluation in the AIDS Healthcare Foundation significantly improved project performance and resource utilization. Danladi and Danladi (2023) also found that budget monitoring in Nigerian NGOs significantly strengthened financial performance, while Akpanowo and Mbobo (2025) highlighted that compliance with monitoring mechanisms under the Fiscal Responsibility Act reinforces fiscal discipline. Additionally, Mobosi and Okonta (2025) emphasized the critical role of monitoring in aligning budgetary decisions with fiscal sustainability, particularly in state governments. The coefficient of 0.290 indicates that improving budget monitoring by one unit results in a 0.290 unit increase in fiscal sustainability, and the p-value of 0.000 confirms that this effect is highly significant, reflecting the central role of continuous oversight in achieving long-term fiscal stability in the Nigerian public sector.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrate that effective budgetary control mechanisms play a crucial role in promoting fiscal sustainability within the Nigerian public sector, highlighting the broader significance of sound financial management practices. The positive and significant effects of the studied variables indicate that when public organizations maintain structured approaches to budgeting, consistently monitor budget performance, and analyze revenue variances, they are better positioned to achieve financial stability and resilience. These outcomes suggest that a disciplined budgeting environment fosters accountability and ensures that resources are allocated efficiently, reducing waste and the risk of mismanagement. Additionally, the strong relationship between budget monitoring and fiscal sustainability points to the importance of continuous oversight, as organizations that actively track their financial activities are more likely to identify and correct deviations before they escalate into systemic challenges. Similarly, consistent revenue variance analysis allows for timely corrective measures, which enhances predictability and strengthens the capacity of public institutions to meet obligations and sustain operations over time. Overall, the findings emphasize that comprehensive budgetary control is not merely a procedural requirement but a fundamental mechanism through which public sector entities can safeguard financial health and sustain long-term fiscal performance. The collective effect of these mechanisms contributes to the stability of government finances, allowing for strategic planning and efficient execution of public programs. By fostering an environment of transparency, disciplined expenditure, and proactive financial management, public institutions can maintain operational continuity, build stakeholder confidence, and create a stable foundation for economic planning. This demonstrates that strong internal control systems within the budgeting process are integral to maintaining fiscal order, ensuring the

sustainability of resources, and enhancing the capacity of government agencies to deliver on their mandates effectively.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it is recommended that management teams in Nigerian public sector organizations should strengthen the preparation and implementation of annual operating budgets by ensuring that budget plans are comprehensive, realistic, and aligned with organizational objectives. This would help guide financial decisions more effectively, ensure optimal allocation of resources, and support long-term fiscal sustainability.

For revenue budget variance analysis, it is recommended that finance departments within public sector agencies establish systematic procedures to regularly review and investigate discrepancies between actual and budgeted revenues. By doing so, management can identify the causes of variances early and implement corrective measures to maintain financial stability and improve the accuracy of future revenue forecasts.

Regarding budget monitoring, it is recommended that supervisory bodies and internal audit units actively track budget performance across all departments using modern monitoring tools and reporting mechanisms. Continuous oversight will enhance accountability, ensure adherence to financial plans, and strengthen the organization's ability to respond to deviations promptly, ultimately reinforcing fiscal discipline and sustaining long-term financial health.

REFERENCES

- Adrison, V. (2024). Fiscal sustainability in Indonesia: Policies and progress. *Asian Economic Policy Review*, 19(2), 224-247.
- Agor, R., Erhuotor, E. E., Musa, A., & Ademu, M. L. (2024). The Dynamics of Federal Government Budget Deficits and Their Impact on Long-Term Economic Stability and Growth in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Sustainability Research*, 2(1), 65-85. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14566681>
- Ajibola, I., Ojeme, S. S., & Akinola, A. A. (2024). Budgetary control and public sector financial management in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*, 4(4), 603–608.
- Akayuri, G. A., Ampong, K., & Apau, S. (2025). Budget and Budgetary Control, a Real Tool for Controlling Public Expenditure in the Context of Public Sector Organization in Ghana. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 10(1), 42-61.
- Akeke, M. M., Atah, C. A., & Akaniniene, D. D. (2024). The Impact of Budget Implementation and Evaluation on Small-Scale Enterprise Operations in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Management*, 2695-1932.
- Akpanowo, R. E., & Mbobo, E. M. (2025). Effect of Fiscal Responsibility Act on budgeting and fiscal discipline in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 13(1), 80–93.
- Anyanwu, F. A., & Ananwude, A. C. (2021). Public Sector Financial Management and Economic Growth Sustainability in Nigeria: 1986 to 2020. *Journal La Bisecoman*, 2(6), 11-22.
- Augustine, A. A. (2022). Budgeting techniques and budgetary control in local governments: Participatory budgeting a critical instrument for sustainable development. *International Journal of Management and Economics Invention*, 8(11), 2682-2693.
- Badara, M. S. (2017). The relevant of contingency theory and stewardship theory on the internal audit research. *Journal of World Economic Research*, 6(2), 17-22.
- Danladi, M. Z., & Danladi, G. P. (2023). Impact of budgetary control on the financial performance of non-profit organization in Nigeria (NGO). *POLAC Management Review*, 3(2), 149–160.
- Dusabimana, J., & Kiptanui, T. T. (2025). Effect of budgetary control practices on financial sustainability of non-governmental organization in Rwanda: A case of Aids Healthcare Foundation. *Journal of Research Innovation and Implications in Education*, 9(2), 663–675.
- Ezekwe, C. I. (2025). Fiscal Sustainability in Nigeria: Does Changes in Oil Prices Matter?. Available at SSRN 5199542.
- Ikwuo, A. K., Nworie, G. O., & Moedu, V. O. (2024). Implementation of AI-driven automation: A game-changer in accounting research. *International Journal of Financial, Accounting, and Management*, 6(3), 385-398. <https://doi.org/10.35912/ijfam.v6i3.2522>
- Mobosi, I. A., & Okonta, P. O. (2025). Revenue structure and budgetary choice in Nigeria: implication for fiscal sustainability of the states government. *International Tax and Public Finance*, 32(3), 828-850.

- Nestor, C., & David, S. E. S. E. (2023). How does growth respond to government budgetary implementation in Nigeria. *FUO Journal of Management Sciences*, 7(Special), 180-189.
- Nwangwu J. C., Ozigbo Ada-Mac. O. Ngige C. D. & Ugwu I. V. (2020). Entrepreneurial skills and youth economic empowerment: a study of small scale and medium scale enterprises (SMAs) in Anambra State. *International Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship (IJME)* 2(1), 51-66. COOU, 2020.
- Nwoko, C.N.J., Okuma, N. C., & Ugwu I. V. (2022). Effect of economic globalization on Nigeria's economic growth (1981-2018), *International Journal of Education and Social Science Research (IJESSR)* 5 (3): 401-421
- Nworie, G. O. & Onwuka, E. M. (2023). Influence of Training and Personnel Development on Organizational Productivity of Manufacturing Firms: Perspective Study of Business Management Academics. *International Journal of Academic Management Science Research*, 7(4), 18-28. <http://ijeais.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/4/IJAMSR230403.pdf>
- Nwoye, U. J., Udunwoke, C. M., & Nworie, G. O. (2023). Debt level and economic performance of Nigeria: effects. *Journal of Global Accounting*, 9(1), 214-247. Retrieved from <https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/index.php/joga/article/view/2068>
- Ogbu, C. G & Ugwu I. V. (2016b). A critical analysis of the relationship between delegation and organization design, authority, responsibility, accountability. *The International Journal of Business & Management (ISSN:2321-8916)*: 4(11), 12-16. www.theibm.com
- Okorie, O. S., & Campus, I. (2016). Budget, Budgeting and Budgetary Control in the Public Sector. *Journal of Accounting, Business and Social sciences*, 1(1), 1-14.
- Okwaro, G. K. (2014). *Budgetary controls and performance of public benefits organizations In Kisumu County, Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- Onyebu, M. C., Ugwu I. V., Oluwafemi, A. M. & Agbo, O. G. (2020). The role of entrepreneurial training in promoting cluster-based micro and small enterprises development in South East Zone, Nigeria. *Journal of African Enterprise and Finance Development*. (ISSN: 2714-3481), (2)1: 156-177, Jun, 2020. www.seedev.org
- Ruliana, T., Soegiarto, E., Yudhyani, E., & Latif, I. N. (2015). Operating budgets as the management control. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 15(3), 269. <https://doi.org/10.XXX>
- Sorochuk, C. M., Wilck, J. H., & Leemis, L. M. (2023). Budget Variance Analysis for Various Numbers and Combinations of Responsibility Centers. *Management Accounting*, 24(2), 122.
- Ugwu, I. V & Nwakoby, N. P. (2021) Empirical study of implementation of ISA 701- Key audit matters: focus on Nigeria firms. *International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 12, December – 2021, Pages:1-12 dftfgui* 3(1)
- Ugwu, I. V., Eboatu, I. & Nwoko, C. N. J. (2022). Implementation of IPSAS accrual basis elements and financial reporting quality: Application of grass-root analyses. *International Journal of Academic Health and Medical Research (IAHMR) ISSN: 2643-9824 Vol. 6 Issue 9, Sept., 2022, Pages: 76-86*
- Ugwu I. V. (2020j). Determinants of disclosure of key audit matters: Post period of IAS 701 in Nigeria. *International Network Organization for Scientific Research. INOSR Arts and Humanities (ISSN: 2705-1676)*, 6(1): 180-204, 2020. <http://www.inosr.net/inosr-and-humanities/>
- Taiwo, A. S., Wahab, T. I., & Nwanbuisi, O. F. (2025). Determinants of Fiscal Policy Sustainability in Nigeria. *Journal of Arid Zone Economy*, 5(7), 104-117.
- The Punch. (2023, October 26). N5.5 tn payroll: FG stops workers' salaries not on IPPIS. *The Punch*. <https://punchng.com/n5-5tn-payroll-fg-stops-workers-salaries-not-on-ippis/>
- Torring, J., & Bentzen, T. Ø. (2020). Does stewardship theory provide a viable alternative to control-fixated performance management? *Administrative Sciences*, 10(4), 86.
- Wanga, V. C. (2022). *Budgetary Control and Financial Sustainability of Local Non-Governmental Organizations in Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).